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Effectiveness of Using Imitation Technique Through English Video Towards Students' English Pronunciation Ability

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to find out whether learning English using imitation video technique can improve the English pronunciation ability of class X high school students who were divided into 2 groups, namely the experimental group and the control group. This study used a samples of 50 students taken from 25 students the experimental class and 25 students from the control class. In this study, the researcher used student records to determine the pre-test and post-test. Furthermore, the results of the two tests were tested statistically using the normality test, homogeneity test, and t-test. The average value in the data shows that the pre-test value in the class that received treatment was 46.24 and the average value in the post-test was 72.88. after being applied to imitate English videos, there was an increase in the average score of students by 26.64. then the results of the t-test showed to t-table with a significant level of 5% was 2.93 and the degrees of freedom (df) were 48, for the t-test score was 3.61. As the t-test value is greater than the t-table value, Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. In measuring the level of effect size with $d = 1.78$ this shows that this study has strong effective in improving students; English pronunciation skills. Therefore, to improve English pronunciation skills, it is highly recommended to use the technique of imitating English videos through YouTube media.

Keywords: *Effectiveness, Imitating English Video, Pronunciation Ability.*

Introduction

Pronunciation is crucial thing in good communication because the wrong pronunciation will guide to negative and misinterpretation impression with the other person. Thus, English pronunciation is one of the most difficult abilities to acquire and learners should spend lots of time to enhance their pronunciation (Gilakjani, 2016). Many international student who study English as a foreign language often make a mistake that they do not pay enough interest to the pronunciation of English. Pronunciation is important factor of speaking and it gives a significant effect on determining the utterance meaning (Aprianto and Heaerazi, 2019). Most of student underestimate the importance of pronunciation because they consider that the pronunciation is less important than other English aspects such as vocabulary, grammar and lexicology. Pronunciation is packet of language aspects that nearly everyone obstinate to learn, remarkably as it becomes a extraneous language. To persuade the adjust pronunciation takes a tough and has to practice costantly. Pronunciation is considered as a sub-skill of speaking (Pourhosein Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2016). However, as the foreign language learners need more and more practice in learning pronunciation.

English language will not be useful in communication properly if the student who is studied English as foreign language have not obtained English pronunciation ability. Learning pronunciation needs a lot of effort and time especially when the EFL learns it as

foreign language, and pronunciation is the most difficult to learn in language aspects. There are some factors that make the excuse why English pronunciation is tough to learn, namely: stress; accent, rhythm and intonation; exposure and motivation; attitude; instruction; personality; age; and mother tongue influence (Pourhosein Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2016). Pronunciation can and must learn and it is an important part of communication that has a key role in communicative language teaching (Gilakjani, 2016). Pronunciation is a crucial aspect of speaking and it gives a significant effect on determining the utterance meaning (Dewi & Ahmad, 2021). (Thir, 2016) opinion that communication disorders or misunderstandings in EFL communication are the reason pronunciation teaching is so important.

These factors are usually have an effect which makes the EFL difficult to learn pronunciation, because English language has a lot of phonemes (sounds) which the mother tongue or the first language of the EFL might did not possess those phonemes. The purpose of learning pronunciation is not ask the students speak like a native speaker, but making the native speakers easily to understand what the EFL means, and the EFL should be have a better intonation and stress when speaks the words. The main goal is that students be understood. Not a perfect accent, but good pronunciation is required (Pourhosein Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2016).

In fact pronunciation capacity is not handy to be extended in lots of schools due to the fact English is a foreign language. Newbies pick the use of their mother tongue inside the school than using English language. Then, their society inside the school do no longer contribute them to use English language. So, new studen hardly ever to use English language inside the clasroom or real speak, and they are fearful of making mistakes when using English. Because of those problems students have problems to apply English language in their life. The ones subjects typically occur in some School in Indonesia for instance country senior high School.

Senior High School is one of the private schools located in the east Surabaya. As a reputable schooling this school affords English language to learners as a topic specifically pronunciation capability in the acquiring technique of English. Further, this school additionally uses the 2013 direction (K13) as a manual for English learning. Based totally on the 2013 curriculum (K13), The reason of gaining knowledge of English in high school is to permit students to have interaction socially by conveying the that means of oral abilities and responding or commenting at the speech, however how do students want to apply English at the same time as they don not realize sound of phrases English.

In teaching pronunciation instructor have to be capable screen the student in a analyzing situation on the way to enable them to understand how to mention the precise sound in English language. It is very clean instructor needs to do something effective while learning pronunciation, aspect that must be acquired with the aid of senior high school. Which means that if the students do not obtained the facets needed in the curriculum, his or her English has no longer been powerful. In fact, within the senior high school, the activity of the English teacher's coaching technique is the dearth of techniques in coaching English, specifically the pronunciation capability. This ends in poor cognition of student in learning English. The English classroom conducts English lessons twice in week, with a length of 90 (2x45) mins and passing grades (KKM), aims to educated and able to explicit monologues as it should be and fluently, engage with people round them rhythmically. This method that if the trainer wants to educate pronunciation, he or she have many techniques for learning pronunciation.

Primarily based on matter above, this study use imitation as practice pronunciation in classroom. Imitating tachment can be very useful in learning proper pronunciation in English for students (Trofimovich, 2016). It is miles apparent that English can become the mother tongue of young stress handiest if they are able to imitate speakers of English. It can be easy

to say that kids examine to talk by using imitation, however there is an extremely good deal of converging proof that has regarded to insist that they learn how to pronounce, as a minimum, this way. Research speculated that even young learners can understand what it means by imitating the language around them and how the language components function (Sarala T.P., at all, 2021). so why must they now not use this talent to manual the manufacturing of the features of their own speech in some manner? Secondly, they also reflect a few seemingly arbitrary styles of speech timing, like the vowel length differences in |sit| down and |seat|. In view that many of those patterns are language precise, this seems to be mainly robust proof for imitation to be gambling a function, for how else could they be discovered? Thirdly, mimicry is something that infants, older children and adults are able to do, and imitation genuinely does play a role in a infant's greater fashionable getting to know of language and of different competencies.

For this reason, imitation is copying the phrases, stress, pauses, intonation, facial features and gestures of native English speaker, it teaches the EFL to pay attention the sounds and to know the styles of English word's sounds, and it trains to make the onses equal sounds by using themselves. All of which means that a toddler is truly now not born with a fully fledged power of imitation. Children have to learn to imitate. It is miles a slow and exhausting procedure. A child learns to imitate in the same way as he learns many other things in his progress towards language: directly and comprehensive copying others thus affords the rapid acquisition of a vast array of essential skills that have been developed and accumulated through multiple past generations (Nielsen, 2018). The imitation supply the EFL hazard to carry out in English and it is like the students turn out to be a local English speaker, and it trains the mouth with the ears. So the EFL must being attentive to the sound and make the identical sounds of the words, and it is not always education with mouth and eyes by way of studying and guessing the pronunciation of words, or this is not education the student's understand of the speaker is saying, however the students are trying out and practising pronunciation on talking ability. without difficulty to try to hold on every day make money working from home by way of the EFL, but it wish full attention to listen. That is helping the scholars have better accent, to clear up pronunciation quick, extra a clearer whilst speak English language, and making students greater assured when communicate English language.

There are previous studies about imitation, (Ibarrola, 2011) with a title "The Effect of Using Two Approaches of Teaching Pronunciation (Intuitive-Imitative and Analytic-Linguistic) on Speaking Fluency among Iranian EFL Learners" The research was conducted in language institute in Sirjan, Iran. The sample of the study comprised 60 EFL learners. Another study is the one conducted by (Prabhu et al., 2015) which is entitled "Imitation Learning: A Ground- Breaking Technique to Enchance English Pronunciation Skills for Slow Bloomers". The observe changed into run in English branch at West Tirunelveli Engineering University, and 7 contributors who have been English teachers have been worried in the study. From the explanation above, this study research was conducted on the effectiveness of imitation English videos using YouTube to improve students' pronunciation ability, with the hope this technique can help students to overcome their lack of speaking skills, especially in pronunciation. This study is entitled "Learning English Pronunciation Through Imitation Video for EFL Students in the English Class of Senior High School.

From the reason above, the research identified a few situations which are How is the effectiveness of using imitation technique through english video towards students' english pronunciation ability?

Literature Review

In human life, language is an important tool because language has a main function, namely to convey certain information and messages. Therefore. The parties involved in the

communication must understand the language clearly. One aspect is the sound produced when people speak or pronunciation. This sound production is studied in phonology. Phonology is relating pronunciation to the basic field of linguistics that deals with the scientific study of the structure of language (Saputri, 2016). Pronunciation is one of the crucial factors in English, because using English to communicate requires pronunciation as a very good communication tool. It is a tool how people use it by using producing some sounds of words, if they need to communicate, they make a few sounds of words. Pronunciation is the production of English sound (Gilakjani, 2016). Learning Pronunciation is the most complicated but important aspect of teaching English. The communication process requires pronunciation, because the success of a communication comes from the correct pronunciation. Poor pronunciation is one factor that makes EFL learners reluctant to speak English (Ambalegin et al., 2017, p. 125).

Imitation is words, stresses, pauses, intonation, facial expressions and movements of native English speech, it teaches EFL to listen to sounds and know the sound patterns of English words, and it trains to make their own sounds (Arsy, 2021). This study uses imitation method to improve pronunciation comprehension. Imitative learning is faster approach in practice because it is used to solve problems and does not require significant space exploration (Raina et al., 2019).

For individual or group study can use video because it can be controlled with pause or repeat. Because that way students can hear the stress, intonation, and rhythm of language along with seeing facial expressions and body language. Multimedia instruction combining video, sound, words, and images together will support meaningful learning and allow students to understand the material better (Mayer, 2014). Thus, it asserts that people learn more deeply from words and pictures than from words alone (Mayer, 2014). YouTube has become one of the most popular websites in the world which has an important role in teaching and learning English. This has been considered as a source of relevant online material (Alexa., 2014). By providing students with everyday language videos and authentic live situations they can improve their understanding, performance and production of the English language.

Method Of The Study

In this study, was used quantitative as a research design. This was used a quasi-experimental design. Quantitative research is an explanation of an issue or event through numerical data collection and aided by some of the statistic feature (Apuke, 2017). That way the researcher was divided two types of class into a quasi-experimental class, the class consists of a control class and an experimental class. In the control class the teaching is not done using imitating, while in the experimental class the teaching is done using imitating English videos. This research was conducted at a senior high school, which is located at Keputih Surabaya. The time of the study has been carried out in February – March 2022. The population used in this study were students of class X SMA, namely class IPS A and IPS B, totaling 50 students. After the data was collected, the researcher analyzed the video recording data obtained based on the standard of pronunciation, dictionary, rubric and English video, then continue with scoring for pre-test and post-test after that entering the scoring into SPSS according to the formula below.

Results And Discussion

This study used video recordings to determine students' pronunciation in English. After that the recordings obtained were analyzed according to English pronunciation standards, rubrics and English videos from YouTube. The recordings obtained from the pre-test of the experimental and control groups before the imitation technique was applied, there were still many pronunciations that did not meet the pronunciation standards and English videos from YouTube. This can be seen from the results of the rubric for assessing pronunciation skills.

Result of Rubric

Student Number	Participant	Pre-test eksperimen	Pre-test control	Pos-test eksperimen	Post-test control
1	S1	62	44	90	46
2	S2	53	38	73	55
3	S3	47	34	62	46
4	S4	52	52	82	87
5	S5	62	45	89	66
6	S6	46	32	82	45
7	S7	41	33	88	43
8	S8	43	34	73	44
9	S9	37	34	73	40
10	S10	41	40	67	76
11	S11	38	42	67	71
12	S12	53	38	70	65
13	S13	33	41	57	56
14	S14	37	41	65	79
15	S15	51	42	80	63
16	S16	43	52	62	80
17	S17	27	33	43	38
18	S18	47	48	75	80
19	S19	53	34	82	52
20	S20	47	52	80	81
21	S21	33	44	73	54
22	S22	62	29	82	54
23	S23	53	37	70	60
24	S24	62	43	82	58
25	S25	33	38	55	45
Total Score		1156	1000	1822	1484

Mean	46,24	40,00	72,88	59,36
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The average score of students obtained from the pre-test was only 46.24 for the experimental group and 40.00 for the control group. However, after the imitation technique was applied, the average score obtained from the post-test of the experimental group experienced a significant increase, this shows that the technique of imitating English videos using YouTube can improve students' English pronunciation skills.

Below is the Cohen's formula that serves to calculate the effect size of the two independent groups of the experimental class and the control class.

Table of Effect Size Test

Mean experimental class	Std.Deviation experimental class	Mean control class	Std.Deviation control class	Cohen's d effect size
72,88	11,461	59,36	14,748	178,5608

From the calculation results above, it can be seen that the effect size reaches 1.78. in the criteria for categorizing Cohen's value when the data has a value above 1.0 indicates that the interpretation is very large. These results indicate that the use of the technique of imitating English videos through YouTube media has a great influence on English learning activities. So it can be concluded that imitating English videos through YouTube media has an effect on students' pronunciation abilities.

Discussion

This study aims to determine the effect of imitating English videos using You Tube media on the English pronunciation of tenth grade of high school students in 2022/2023. In this study, the sample used was 25 students from each experimental class and control class, and the results obtained from each class had a positive impact. The average score obtained from the experimental class during the pre-test was 46.24 and after receiving treatment, the average post-test result increased to 72.88. For the control class the average value at the time of the pre-test was 40.00 and the average post-test was 59,36. From the increase in the average results, it can be compared that the experimental class has a significant impact compared to the control class, this shows that the experimental class gives better results than the control class.

Next, the researcher applies the sample t-test using the t-test calculation method which aims to get the sig or p value (2-tailed)= 0.001. The test shows that the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted because the p-value is (0.000) and is lower than sig a = 0.05. This means thaat this research has a significant effect in improving English pronunciation skills using the technique of imitating English videos via YouTube.

In addition, researchers used Cohen's d formula to measure the effectiveness of the technique of imitating English videos through YouTube media. In this study, researcher found a significant effect of using the technique of imitating English videos using YouTube media, the effectiveness level was 1.7.

In this study, the technique of imitating English using YouTube media helps students to improve students' pronunciation skills. With the conclusion that the technique of imitating English through YouTube has a significant effect on students' English pronunciation.

Conclusion

In the previous chapter, it has been shown that the technique of imitating English videos using YouTube has a significant effect on students' English pronunciation. This is known from the results of the pre-test and post-test in the experimental class and the control class. For the average results of the pre-test in the experimental and control classes, there was only a slight difference, based on table 4.8 shows the pre-test results in the control class are 40.00 and the pre-test results in the experimental class are 46.24. However, after the action was given, the average post-test result in the experimental class had a higher score than the control class. Based on table 4.9 shows the results that $\text{sig } 0.01 < 0.05$, or H_0 is rejected. From the whole series of data tests it can be concluded that the use of the technique of Imitating English Video Through YouTube has a significant effect on the development of English pronunciation for tenth graders of Senior High School.

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